

Supplementary Information

Synthesis of Enantioenriched Amines by Iron-Catalysed Amination of Alcohols Employing at Least One Achiral Substrate

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General methods

Chromatography and spectroscopy

Column chromatography was performed using Merck silica gel type 9385 230-400 mesh and typically pentane and ethyl acetate or ethyl acetate and methanol as eluent.

TLC: Merck silica gel 60, 0.25 mm. The components were visualized by UV or KMnO₄ staining.

Gas Chromatography: enantiomeric ratio of the chiral products was determined by chiral GC and HPLC. Chiral GC analyses were performed using an Agilent Technologies 7890A instrument equipped with a CP Chirasil Dex CB column (25m × 0.25mm × 0.25 μm) and an FID detector. Product analysis was performed by GC-FID equipped with an HP-5MS column (30m × 0.25mm × 0.25 μm) and a GC-MS Shimadzu also equipped with an HP-5MS column (30m × 0.25mm × 0.25 μm). HPLC analyses were performed using a UFLC Shimadzu instrument equipped with a PDA detector.

Mass spectrometry: Mass spectra were recorded on an AEI-MS-902 mass spectrometer (EI⁺) or an LTQ Orbitrap XL (ESI⁺).

NMR spectroscopy: ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Mercury Plus 400, Agilent MR 400 (400 and 101 MHz, respectively) using CDCl₃ and C₆D₆ as a solvent. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at room temperature. Chemical shift values are reported in ppm with the solvent resonance as the internal standard (CDCl₃: 7.26 for ¹H, 77.16 for ¹³C; C₆D₆: 7.15 for ¹H, 128.06 for ¹³C). Data are reported as follows: chemical shifts, multiplicity (s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, br. = broad, m = multiplet), coupling constants (Hz), and integration.

Optical rotations were determined using a Schmidt + Haensch polarimeter (polartronic MH8).

All reactions were carried out under an Argon atmosphere using oven (120 °C) dried glassware and using standard Schlenk techniques. Complexes **C1** and **C2** were synthesized according to the literature procedure.^[1] Ni(OTf)₂ (min. 98%) was purchased from Strem chemicals. Anhydrous Me₃NO was purchased from TCI chemicals. Toluene was dried and degassed through a MB SPS solvent purification system, while other solvents were degassed by 3 freeze-thaw cycles from commercial anhydrous sources. All other reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Acros and TCI in reagent or higher grade and were used as received without further purification.

Representative procedures

General procedure for the iron-catalyzed alkylation of amines with alcohols

An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged with the cyclopentadienone iron complex **C1** (0.03 mmol, 6 mol%) and Me₃NO (0.03 mmol, 6 mol%) or **C2** (0.03 mmol, 6 mol%) was evacuated and backfilled with argon for three times, then the amine (0.5 mmol), alcohol (4 equivalent, unless otherwise stated in the manuscript) and degassed toluene (2 mL) were sequentially added. The mixture was stirred at 135 °C (temperature of the oil bath) for the indicated time (typically 24 h) and then cooled down to room temperature. The solution was filtered over celite and analyzed by GC to determine the conversion of the starting amine. The product was isolated by column chromatography on silica gel with pentane/ethyl acetate as eluent mixture and the enantiomeric

excess of the amine product was determined by either chiral GC or HPLC (see details for each compound below).

Procedure for the monitoring of the reaction between *p*-anisidine and (*S*)-2-methylbutanol

Four parallel reactions were prepared in 25 mL Schlenk tubes by dissolving *p*-anisidine (**6a**, 0.15 mmol, 19.0 mg), (*S*)-2-methylbutanol (**1b**, 0.6 mmol, 0.065 mL) and dodecane (0.044 mmol, 10 μ L) in toluene (0.8 mL). The reaction mixtures were stirred at 135 °C for the desired amount of time (2 h, 4 h, 8 h, 18 h) and the same procedure was repeated in the presence of molecular sieves (4Å, 50 mg). The conversion and the product yield were calculated by the internal standard method and the enantiomeric excess of the product was determined by chiral HPLC (Lux Cellulose 3, heptane:*i*-PrOH 99:1, isocratic elution, 254 nm, PDA detector).

Supplementary Note 1: Additional ¹H NMR studies in order to clarify the possible imine-enamine racemization pathway

In the experiments **A-C** we assumed to see any indications for the imine-enamine equilibrium, however, except the formation of the imine in all cases (**A-C**), no enamine formation was observed under these conditions.

Procedures for (A-C): An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged with (*S*)-2-methylbutanal (0.2 mmol, 17.2 mg or 21.2 μ L) and *p*-anisidine (0.2 mmol, 24.6 mg) and toluene-d₈ (as a solvent, 1 mL), molecular sieves (150-200 mg, experiment **B**) or Me₃NO (10 mol%, experiment **C**). Solid materials were weighed into the Schlenk tube under air. Then the Schlenk tube was subsequently connected to an argon line and vacuum-argon exchange was performed three times. Liquid starting materials and solvent were charged under an argon stream. The Schlenk tube was capped and the mixture was rapidly stirred at room temperature for 1 min, then was placed into a pre-heated oil bath (135 °C) and stirred for 6 hours. Then, the reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature. Preparing the sample, 0.6 mL of the reaction mixture was placed to a *J*-Young NMR tube under argon.

Supplementary Note 2: Additional ¹H NMR studies in order to clarify the possible aldehyde-enol racemization pathway

In the experiments **D-F** we aimed to observe any indications that could prove the aldehyde-enol tautomerization. While in experiment **D** no enol formation was detected, experiments **E-F** revealed its generation. The obtained data is completely in line with our previous experiments, namely the reaction between (*S*)-2-methylbutanol and **C1** in presence of Me₃NO generated a small amount of (*S*)-2-methylbutyraldehyde in racemic form, which we previously identified by chiral GC.

Procedures for (D-F): An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged with (*S*)-2-methylbutanal (0.2 mmol, 17.2 mg or 21.2 μ L) and toluene-d₈ (as a solvent, 1 mL), molecular sieves (150-200 mg, experiment **E**) or Me₃NO (10 mol%, experiment **F**). Then the Schlenk tube was subsequently connected to an argon line and vacuum-argon exchange was performed three times. Liquid starting materials and solvent were charged under an argon stream. The Schlenk tube was capped and the mixture was rapidly stirred at room temperature for 1 min, then was placed into a pre-heated oil bath (135 °C) and stirred for 6 hours. Then, the reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature. Preparing the sample, 0.6 mL of the reaction mixture was placed to a *J*-Young NMR tube under argon.

Based on these results, it is very likely that in this system, with this combination of amine/alcohol substrates, the racemization takes place through the aldehyde/enol isomerization.

Supplementary Note 3: Experiments to determine the optical purity of the imine

Procedures A and B: The same procedure as described in **Supplementary Note 1** was followed. At the end of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature and analyzed by GC-MS for confirming imine formation and purity, and HPLC for enantiomeric excess determination. The synthesis of (*S*)-2-methylbutanal was performed following the method developed by Stahl and coworkers. [Hoover, J.M., Stahl, S.S. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, 133, 16901–16910].

HPLC traces of the imines:

HPLC Analysis parameters:

- Column: Chiralcel OD-H, 4.6 mm x 250 mm; 5 μ m particle size
- Eluent: Heptane/2-Propanol, 99:1 isocratic; each containing 0.1% (v/v) diethylamine
- Flow rate: 0.3 mL/min
- Column temperature: 15 °C
- Run time: 60 min

HPLC Chromatogram Procedure A

GC-MS trace Procedure A

HPLC Chromatogram Procedure B

GC-MS trace Procedure B

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1: Plot of *ee* vs time in the reaction between *p*-anisidine (**6a**) and (*S*)-2-methylbutanol (**1b**) in absence/presence of molecular sieves. General reaction conditions: 0.15 mmol **6a**, 0.6 mmol **1b**, 6 mol% **C1**, 6 mol% Me₃NO, 1 mL toluene, 135 °C, 0.01 mL dodecane as an internal standard.

The obtained data is summarized in the table:

Entry	Time, h	Enantiomeric excess, %	
		Without mol sieves	With mol sieves
1	0	100	100
2	1	97	74
3	3	93	50
4	6	92	37
5	20	84	14

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1: *N*-alkylation of (*S*)-1-cyclohexylethan-1-amine (**2l**) with 1-pentanol (**1a**).

Entry	Amine, equiv.	Alcohol, equiv.	Time, h	Temp., °C	Conv., %	Mono-Alk. Amine, %	Di-Alk. Amine, %
1	1	4	24	110	-	-	-
2	1	4	8	135	56	28	6

General reaction conditions: (*S*)-1-cyclohexylethan-1-amine (**2l**, 0.3 mmol), 1-pentanol (**1a**, 1.2 mmol, 4 equiv.), toluene (2 mL), **C1** (6 mol%), Me₃NO (6 mol%), 110 °C or 135 °C, 8 h or 24 h. GC yields are shown. These experiments were conducted during the revision process, with a different bath of **C1**.

Supplementary Table 2: *N*-alkylation of various amines with alcohols.

Entry	Amine	Alcohol	Yield, %
1	2a 	1c Methanol	-
2	2a 	1d Ethanol	20
3	2a 	1e Ph-CH=CH-CH ₂ -OH	38
4	2a 	1f 	16
5	2a 	1g 	68
6	2p 	1b 	41
7	2g 	4f 	68

General reaction conditions: amine (0.3 mmol), alcohol (1.2 mmol, 4 equiv.), toluene (2 mL), **C1** (6 mol%), Me₃NO (6 mol%), 135 °C, 24 h. GC yields are shown. These experiments were conducted during the revision process, with a different bath of **C1**.

Spectral data of isolated compounds

(*R*)-*N*-(1-phenylethyl)pentan-1-amine (3a)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 84 mg, 88%, 99% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.36-7.28 (m, 4H), 7.28-7.21 (m, 1H), 3.76 (q, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 1H), 2.54-2.37 (m, 2H), 1.60 (*br s*, 1H), 1.54-1.39 (m, 2H), 1.36 (d, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 3H), 1.32-1.20 (m, 4H), 0.87 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): 145.8, 128.4, 126.8, 126.5, 58.4, 47.9, 30.0, 29.6, 24.3, 22.6, 14.0.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₃H₂₁NH⁺ [*M*+H⁺]: 192.1752; found: 192.1748.

[α]_D: +44.0° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess of the acetyl derivative was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 10 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 200 °C, 10 min). Retention times: 29.2 min (minor), 29.3 min (major).

(*R*)-*N*-(1-(3-chlorophenyl)ethyl)pentan-1-amine (3b)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 97 mg, 86%, 99% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.31 (t, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.27-7.17 (m, 3H), 3.73 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 2.51-2.43 (m, 1H), 2.42-2.34 (m, 1H), 1.50-1.40 (m, 2H), 1.33 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 1.30-1.21 (m, 4H), 0.87 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 148.1, 134.2, 129.7, 126.9, 126.7, 124.8, 58.1, 47.9, 29.9, 29.5, 24.4, 22.6, 14.0.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₃H₂₁ClNH⁺ [*M*+H⁺]: 226.1363, found: 226.1357.

[α]_D: +44.5° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess of the acetyl derivative was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 5 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 150 °C, 15 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 180 °C, 10 min). Retention times: 43.7 (minor), 44.2 min (major).

(*R*)-*N*-(1-(3-methoxyphenyl)ethyl)pentan-1-amine (3c)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 93 mg, 84%, 99% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.23 (t, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 6.92-6.86 (m, 2H), 6.78 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 3.73 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 2.54-2.38 (m, 2H), 1.72 (*br s*, 1H), 1.54-1.39 (m, 2H), 1.35 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H), 1.32-1.20 (m, 4H), 0.87 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): 159.8, 147.6, 129.3, 118.9, 112.1, 112.0, 58.4, 55.2, 47.9, 29.9, 29.6, 24.3, 22.6, 14.0.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₄H₂₃ONH⁺ [M+H⁺]: 222.1858, found: 222.1851.

[α]_D: +40.9° (c 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess of the acetyl derivative was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 5 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 150 °C, 15 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 180 °C, 10 min). Retention times: 46.7 (minor), 47.1 min (major).

(R)-N-(1-(3-fluorophenyl)ethyl)pentan-1-amine (3d)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 85 mg, 81%, 99% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.29-7.22 (m, 1H), 7.09-7.01 (m, 2H), 6.93-6.87 (m, 1H), 3.74 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 2.52-2.35 (m, 2H), 1.51-1.38 (m, 2H), 1.32 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 1.30-1.20 (m, 4H), 0.87 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 163.09 (d, *J* = 245.3 Hz), 148.89 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz), 129.72 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz), 122.16 (d, *J* = 2.6 Hz), 113.54 (d, *J* = 21.2 Hz), 113.23 (d, *J* = 21.3 Hz), 58.05 (d, *J* = 1.9 Hz), 47.85, 29.95, 29.51, 24.36, 22.57, 13.99.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₃H₂₀FNH⁺ [M+H⁺]: 210.1654; found: 210.1658.

[α]_D: +35.4° (c 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess of the acetyl derivative was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 5 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 150 °C, 15 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 180 °C, 10 min). Retention times: 35.5 (minor), 35.9 (major).

(R)-N-(1-(4-chlorophenyl)ethyl)pentan-1-amine (3e)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 80 mg, 71%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.30-7.22 (m, 4H), 3.72 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 2.50-2.42 (m, 1H), 2.40-2.32 (m, 1H), 1.48-1.37 (m, 2H), 1.31 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 1.29-1.22 (m, 4H), 0.86 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 144.39, 132.27, 128.48, 127.93, 57.82, 47.83, 29.90, 29.51, 24.40, 22.57, 14.00.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₃H₂₁ClNH⁺ [M+H⁺]: 226.1363, found: 226.1361.

[α]_D: +43.5° (c 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess of the acetyl derivative was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 10 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 200 °C, 20 min). Retention times: 28.8 (minor), 29.0 min (major).

(R)-N-(1-(4-methoxyphenyl)ethyl)pentan-1-amine (3f)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 69 mg, 62%, 99% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.22 (m, 2H), 6.86 (m, 2H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 3.70 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 2.51-2.43 (m, 1H), 2.42-2.35 (m, 1H), 1.54-1.39 (m, 3H), 1.32 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 1.29-1.23 (m, 4H), 0.86 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 158.41, 137.91, 127.52, 113.70, 113.68, 57.70, 55.21, 47.83, 29.93, 29.57, 24.31, 22.60, 14.04.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₄H₂₃ONH⁺ [*M*+H⁺]: 222.1858, found 222.1852.

[α]_D: +47.3° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess of the acetyl derivative was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 5 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 150 °C, 15 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 180 °C, 10 min). Retention times: 30.6 (minor), 30.8 min (major).

(*R*)-*N*-(1-(4-fluorophenyl)ethyl)pentan-1-amine (3g)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 94 mg, 90%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.30-7.23 (m, 2H), 7.03-6.95 (m, 2H), 3.73 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 2.51-2.42 (m, 1H), 2.41-2.32 (m, 1H), 1.50-1.38 (m, 3H), 1.31 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 1.29-1.20 (m, 4H), 0.86 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 161.71 (d, *J* = 243.9 Hz), 141.52, 127.95 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz), 115.06 (d, *J* = 21.0 Hz), 57.71, 47.81, 29.90, 29.52, 24.44, 22.56, 13.99.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₃H₂₀FNH⁺ [*M*+H⁺]: 210.1658, found: 210.1651.

[α]_D: +39.2° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess of the acetyl derivative was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 5 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 150 °C, 15 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 180 °C, 10 min). Retention times: 36.3 (minor), 36.7 min (major).

(*S*)-*N*-(1-phenylpropyl)pentan-1-amine (3h)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as colourless oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 89 mg, 87%, 99% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.34-7.20 (m, 5H), 3.47 (dd, *J* = 8.2, 5.9 Hz, 1H), 2.48-2.34 (m, 2H), 1.82-1.70 (m, 1H), 1.69-1.56 (m, 1H), 1.53-1.38 (m, 3H), 1.32-1.19 (m, 4H), 0.86 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 0.80 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 144.35, 128.19, 127.28, 126.76, 65.22, 47.82, 30.95, 29.95, 29.54, 22.58, 14.01, 10.80.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₄H₂₃NH⁺ [*M*+H⁺]: 206.1909; found: 206.1907.

[α]_D: -32.5° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess of the acetyl derivative was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 5 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 150 °C, 15 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 180 °C, 10 min). Retention times: 37.3 (major), 37.4 min (minor).

(R)-N-(1-(naphthalen-1-yl)ethyl)pentan-1-amine (3i)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 95 mg, 79%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 8.20 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.88 (dd, *J* = 7.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.75 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 7.66 (d, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 1H), 7.55-7.45 (m, 3H), 4.64 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 2.58 (qt, *J* = 11.3, 7.2 Hz, 2H), 1.54 (m, 2H), 1.50 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 1.33-1.25 (m, 4H), 0.88 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 141.43, 133.95, 131.33, 128.95, 127.05, 125.70, 125.24, 122.91, 122.56, 53.65, 48.10, 30.15, 29.60, 23.62, 22.62, 14.04.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₇H₂₃NH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 242.1909; found: 242.1908.

[α]_D: -39.5° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Lux Cellulose-3 column, 99.5:0.5 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 14.0 min (major), 20.9 min (minor).

(R)-N-pentyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-amine (3j)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as orange oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 67 mg, 66%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.49-7.42 (m, 1H), 7.26-7.17 (m, 3H), 4.35 (t, *J* = 6.1 Hz, 1H), 3.13-3.01 (m, 1H), 2.89-2.77 (m, 1H), 2.77-2.65 (m, 2H), 2.46-2.34 (m, 1H), 2.06-1.92 (m, 1H), 1.68-1.54 (m, 2H), 1.37-1.24 (m, 4H), 0.89 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 145.38, 143.62, 127.29, 126.15, 124.74, 124.07, 63.29, 47.46, 33.58, 30.38, 30.22, 29.67, 22.65, 14.09.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₄H₂₁NH [*M*+*H*⁺]: 204.1752; found: 204.1745.

[α]_D: +4.5° (*c* 0.5, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Chiralpak AD column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 10.9 min (major), 12.3 (minor).

(S)-N-pentyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalen-1-amine (3k)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 81 mg, 75%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.37-7.31 (m, 1H), 7.18-7.11 (m, 2H), 7.10-7.05 (m, 1H), 3.77 (t, *J* = 4.9 Hz, 1H), 2.87-2.77 (m, 1H), 2.76-2.60 (m, 3H), 2.02-1.91 (m, 1H), 1.90-1.84 (m, 2H), 1.77-1.67 (m, 1H), 1.57-1.48 (m, 2H), 1.36-1.28 (m, 4H), 0.90 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 139.63, 137.51, 129.19, 128.85, 126.70, 125.81, 55.61, 47.55, 30.39, 29.83, 29.53, 28.51, 22.81, 19.13, 14.24.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₅H₂₃NH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 218.1909, found: 218.1902.

[α]_D: -7.4° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Chiralpak AD column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 7.6 min (major), 9.0 (minor).

(S)-N-(1-cyclohexylethyl)pentan-1-amine (3l)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 61 mg, 62%, 95% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 2.61 (dt, *J* = 11.1, 7.3 Hz, 1H), 2.52-2.38 (m, 2H), 1.78-1.70 (m, 2H), 1.70-1.61 (m, 2H), 1.46 (p, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 1.37-1.08 (m, 9H), 1.05-0.98 (m, 2H) 0.97 (d, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 3H), 0.89 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 57.86, 47.66, 42.84, 30.12, 30.02, 29.68, 27.90, 26.78, 26.67, 26.51, 22.64, 16.75, 14.05.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₃H₂₇NH⁺ [M+H⁺]: 198.2222; found: 198.2215.

[α]_D: +6.1° (*c* 0.5, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 5 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 150 °C, 15 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 180 °C, 10 min). Retention times: 25.6 (major), 26.1 min (minor).

(R)-N-(3,3-dimethylbutan-2-yl)pentan-1-amine (3m)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 52 mg, 61%, 95% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 2.70 (m, 1H), 2.40 (m, 1H), 2.21 (q, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.49-1.40 (m, 2H), 1.34-1.22 (m, 5H), 0.94 (d, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 3H), 0.88 (t, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 3H), 0.86 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 62.35, 49.01, 34.20, 30.01, 29.64, 26.45, 22.63, 14.87, 14.07.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₁H₂₅NH [M+H⁺]: 172.2065; found: 172.2058.

[α]_D: +8.6° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, 5 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 150 °C, 15 min, ramp of 5 °C/min up to 180 °C, 10 min). Retention times: 19.3 (major), 19.6 min (minor).

(S)-N,N-dipentyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalen-1-amine (3n)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light-yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 95:5, 108 mg, 75%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.77 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.15 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.10 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.05 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 4.09-3.80 (m, 1H), 2.84-2.67 (m, 2H), 2.47-2.28 (m, 4H), 2.06-1.93 (m, 2H), 1.73-1.54 (m, 2H), 1.50-1.38 (m, 4H), 1.38-1.14 (m, 8H), 0.88 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 6H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 140.27, 138.49, 128.59, 128.28, 125.90, 125.65, 58.95, 50.35, 30.26, 29.80, 29.04, 22.85, 22.65, 21.35, 14.29.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₂₀H₃₃NH⁺ [M+H⁺]: 288.2691; found: 288.2689.

[α]_D: +8.6° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Chiralpak OD column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 6.4 (minor), 6.7 (major).

(R)-N-pentyl-N-(1-phenylethyl)pentan-1-amine (3o)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 95:5, 81 mg, 62%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.38-7.27 (m, 4H), 7.24-7.18 (m, 1H), 3.83 (q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 2.49-2.28 (m, 4H), 1.46-1.37 (m, 4H), 1.36-1.30 (m, 3H), 1.30-1.17 (m, 8H), 0.87 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 6H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 147.62, 130.51, 130.38, 129.00, 61.66, 52.56, 32.30, 30.00, 25.27, 19.32, 16.76.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₈H₃₁NH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 262.2535; found: 262.2533.

[α]_D: +2.2° (*c* 0.3, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Chiralpak OD column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 7.2 min (major), 7.4 (minor).

(R)-1-(1-(4-fluorophenyl)ethyl)pyrrolidine (5a)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 66 mg, 68%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.30-7.24 (m, 2H), 6.99-6.92 (m, 2H), 3.14 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 2.54-2.46 (m, 2H), 2.36-2.28 (m, 2H), 1.79-1.67 (m, 4H), 1.35 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 161.66 (d, *J* = 244.2 Hz), 141.41 (d, *J* = 3.1 Hz), 128.53 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz), 114.92 (d, *J* = 21.0 Hz), 65.17, 52.90, 27.76, 23.36, 23.23, 22.16.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₂H₁₆FNH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 194.1345; found: 194.1342.

[α]_D: +8.9° (*c* 0.5, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral GC (Chirasil Dex column, 100 °C, ramp of 0.5 °C/min up to 120 °C, 5 min, ramp of 10 °C/min up to 150 °C, 20 min). Retention times: 31.5 (major), 32.9 min (minor).

(R)-1-(1-(4-fluorophenyl)ethyl)piperidine (5b)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 93 mg, 90%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.29-7.22 (m, 2H), 7.02-6.95 (m, 2H), 3.38 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 2.43-2.25 (m, 4H), 1.59-1.50 (m, 4H), 1.43-1.35 (m, 2H), 1.34 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): 161.65 (d, *J* = 244.1 Hz), 139.59, 129.07 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz), 114.72 (d, *J* = 21.0 Hz), 64.36, 51.38, 26.22, 24.56, 19.35.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₃H₁₈FNH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 208.1502; found: 208.1498.

[α]_D: +21.5° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, ramp of 0.5 °C/min up to 120 °C, 5 min, ramp of 10 °C/min up to 150 °C, 20 min). Retention times: 41.4 (major), 42.8 min (minor).

(R)-1-(1-(4-fluorophenyl)ethyl)azepane (5c)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 93 mg, 84%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.36-7.29 (m, 2H), 7.02-6.94 (m, 2H), 3.75 (q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 2.63-2.56 (m, 4H), 1.62-1.51 (m, 8H), 1.33 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 161.53 (d, *J* = 243.8 Hz), 140.64, 128.91 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz), 114.61 (d, *J* = 20.9 Hz), 62.43, 51.90, 28.94, 26.99, 17.91.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₄H₂₀FNH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 222.1658; found: 222.1656.

[α]_D: +3.6° (*c* 0.5, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, ramp of 0.5 °C/min up to 120 °C, 5 min, ramp of 10 °C/min up to 150 °C, 20 min). Retention times: 58.4 (major), 59.1 min (minor).

(R)-1-(1-(4-fluorophenyl)ethyl)-4-methylpiperidine (5d)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 87 mg, 79%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.29-7.22 (m, 2H), 7.02-6.94 (m, 2H), 3.38 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.03-2.95 (m, 1H), 2.76-2.69 (m, 1H), 1.96-1.87 (m, 1H), 1.83-1.74 (m, 1H), 1.68-1.48 (m, 2H), 1.34 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H), 1.31-1.08 (m, 3H), 0.88 (d, *J* = 5.9 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 164.32 (d, *J* = 244.1 Hz), 142.46 (d, *J* = 3.0 Hz), 131.68 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz), 117.39 (d, *J* = 21.0 Hz), 66.79, 53.64, 53.37, 37.24, 37.21, 33.54, 24.53, 22.22.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₄H₂₀FNH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 222.1658; found: 222.1651.

[α]_D: +26.0° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral GC (Chiralsil Dex column, 100 °C, ramp of 0.5 °C/min up to 120 °C, 5 min, ramp of 10 °C/min up to 150 °C, 20 min). Retention times: 47.4 (major), 47.9 min (minor).

(R)-6-(1-(4-fluorophenyl)ethyl)-6,7-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[*c,e*]azepine (5e)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10, 52 mg, 33%, 98% *ee*; using 10 mol% Ni(OTf)₂: 127 mg, 80%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.53-7.48 (m, 2H), 7.47-7.40 (m, 4H), 7.39-7.33 (m, 2H), 7.30-7.27 (m, 2H), 7.09-7.02 (m, 2H), 3.60 (q, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.50 (d, *J* = 12.5 Hz, 2H), 3.28 (d, *J* = 12.5 Hz, 2H), 1.44 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 161.79 (d, *J* = 244.6 Hz), 141.77 (d, *J* = 3.3 Hz), 141.20, 135.02, 129.70, 128.90 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz), 127.93, 127.54 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz), 115.35 (d, *J* = 21.0 Hz), 61.66, 53.04, 22.73.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₂₂H₂₀FNH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 318.1658; found: 318.1656.

The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.^[2]

[α]_D: +33.8° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Chiralpak AD column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 9.4 min (major), 10.0 (minor).

(R)-Fendiline

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as light brown oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 80:20, 128 mg, 81%, 99% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.35-7.14 (m, 15H), 4.00 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 3.70 (q, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 1H), 2.55-2.39 (m, 2H), 2.33-2.14 (m, 2H), 1.40 (*br s*, 1H), 1.32 (d, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 145.67, 144.98, 144.70, 128.42, 128.37, 127.87, 127.76, 126.80, 126.51, 126.13, 126.12, 58.15, 49.02, 46.01, 36.05, 24.35.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₂₃H₂₅NH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 316.2065; found: 316.2061.

The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.^[3]

[α]_D: +32.7° (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Lux Cellulose-1 column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 21.5 min (major), 25.8 (minor).

(R)-Cinacalcet

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 80:20, 109 mg, 61%, 98% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 8.20 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.89 (dd, *J* = 8.1, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.77 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 7.66 (dd, *J* = 7.2, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.55-7.46 (m, 3H), 7.46-7.41 (m, 2H), 7.38-7.30 (m, 2H), 4.64

(q, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 1H), 2.79-2.55 (m, 4H), 1.85 (p, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H, overlapping with NH), 1.51 (d, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 3H).

^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 101 MHz): δ 145.74, 143.82, 136.65, 134.42 (q, $J = 1.4$ Hz), 133.96, 133.22 (q, $J = 31.9$ Hz), 131.64, 131.32, 129.86, 128.42, 128.34, 127.98, 127.69 (q, $J = 3.7$ Hz), 125.57, 125.33, 125.28 (q, $J = 3.7$ Hz), 56.42, 49.92, 36.08, 34.52, 26.26.

HRMS (EI^+) calculated for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{F}_3\text{NH}$ [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$]: 358.1783; found: 358.1778.

The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.^[4]

[α]_D: +20.0° (c 1.0, CHCl_3)

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Lux Cellulose-3 column, 99.5:0.5 heptane:isopropanol, 1 mL/min. Retention times: 17.0 min (major), 19.3 (minor).

(S)-4-methoxy-N-(2-methylbutyl)aniline (7a)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 95:5, 30 mg, 63%, 80% *ee*; using **C2** (10 mol%): 26 mg, 54%, 96% *ee*).

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz): δ 6.78 (m, 2H), 6.61 (m, 2H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 3.05-2.98 (m, 1H), 2.89-2.81 (m, 1H), 1.72-1.62 (m, 1H), 1.55-1.43 (m, 1H), 1.27-1.15 (m, 1H), 0.97 (d, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 3H), 0.93 (d, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H).

^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 101 MHz): δ 152.1, 142.5, 114.9, 114.2, 55.9, 51.2, 34.4, 27.3, 17.6, 11.3.

HRMS (EI^+) calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{19}\text{NOH}^+$ [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$]: 194.1545; found: 194.1538.

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Lux Cellulose-1 column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 39.9 min (major), 46.5 (minor).

(S)-4-methyl-N-(2-methylbutyl)aniline (7b)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 95:5, 19 mg, 42%, 94% *ee*).

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz): δ 6.91 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 2H), 6.48 (d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 2H), 2.96 (dd, $J = 12.2$, 6.0 Hz, 1H), 2.80 (dd, $J = 12.2$, 7.2 Hz, 1H), 2.16 (s, 3H), 1.64-1.54 (m, 1H), 1.48-1.37 (m, 1H), 1.22-1.06 (m, 1H), 0.89 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 3H), 0.85 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 3H).

^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 101 MHz): δ 146.33, 129.69, 126.14, 112.83, 50.35, 34.44, 27.32, 20.36, 17.56, 11.33.

HRMS (EI^+) calculated for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{19}\text{NH}^+$ [$\text{M}+\text{H}^+$]: 178.1596; found 178.1592.

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Lux Cellulose-1 column, 99.9:0.2 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 29.0 (major), 32.1 (minor).

(S)-N-(2-methylbutyl)benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-amine (7c)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 95:5, 37 mg, 71%, 80% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 6.65 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 6.24 (d, *J* = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 6.04 (dd, *J* = 8.3, 2.3 Hz, 1H), 5.84 (s, 2H), 2.99 (dd, *J* = 12.0, 6.0 Hz, 1H), 2.82 (dd, *J* = 12.1, 7.2 Hz, 1H), 1.71-1.59 (m, 1H), 1.54-1.42 (m, 1H), 1.28-1.14 (m, 1H), 0.96 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H), 0.93 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 150.97, 147.12, 141.92, 111.26, 106.87, 103.14, 98.42, 53.68, 37.11, 29.97, 20.21, 13.96.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₂H₁₉NH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 178.1596; found 178.1592.

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Lux Cellulose-1 column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 29.3 min (major), 31.1 min (minor).

(S)-N-(2-methylbutyl)aniline (7d)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 95:5, 21 mg, 52%, 90% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.17 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 2H), 6.68 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 1H), 6.61 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 2H), 3.05 (dd, *J* = 12.2, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 2.89 (dd, *J* = 12.2, 7.2 Hz, 1H), 1.73-1.62 (m, 1H), 1.56-1.44 (m, 1H), 1.27-1.15 (m, 1H), 0.97 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 0.93 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 151.08, 131.86, 119.75, 115.43, 52.73, 37.11, 29.97, 20.21, 13.96.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₁H₁₇NH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 164.1439; found: 164.1433.

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Lux Cellulose-1 column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 16.8 min (major), 19.4 (minor).

(S)-4-fluoro-N-(2-methylbutyl)aniline (7e)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 95:5, 17 mg, 38%, 76% *ee*; using **C2** (10 mol%): 10 mg, 22%, 99% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 6.91-6.84 (m, 2H), 6.57-6.49 (m, 2H), 3.59 (*br s*, 1H), 3.01 (dd, *J* = 12.1, 6.0 Hz, 1H), 2.85 (dd, *J* = 12.0, 7.2 Hz, 1H), 1.72-1.59 (m, 1H), 1.56-1.43 (m, 1H), 1.28-1.15 (m, 1H), 0.97 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H), 0.93 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 155.57 (d, *J* = 234.2 Hz), 144.94 (d, *J* = 1.7 Hz), 115.57 (d, *J* = 22.3 Hz), 113.37 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz), 50.67, 34.45, 27.30, 17.55, 11.32.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₁H₁₆FNH⁺ [*M*+*H*⁺]: 182.1345; found 182.1341.

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Lux Cellulose-1 column, 99:1 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 15.9 min (major), 19.8 (minor).

(S)-4-((2-methylbutyl)amino)phenol (7f)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 90:10 to 70:30, 30 mg, 68%, 20% *ee*; using **C2** (10 mol%): 32 mg, 71%, 24% *ee*).

¹H NMR (C₆D₆, 400 MHz): δ 6.84-6.63 (m, 2H), 6.49-6.30 (m, 2H), 4.35 (m, 2H), 2.84-2.52 (m, 2H), 1.47-1.22 (m, 2H), 1.05-0.90 (m, 1H), 0.84-0.70 (m, 6H).

¹³C NMR (C₆D₆, 101 MHz): δ 148.99, 142.67, 116.69, 115.12, 51.59, 34.64, 27.55, 17.55, 11.47.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₁H₁₇NOH⁺ [M+H⁺]: 180.1388; found 180.1381.

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Lux Cellulose-1 column, 97:3 heptane:isopropanol, 1 mL/min. Retention times: 39.5 (major), 41.9 (minor).

(R)-4-methoxy-N-(2-phenylpropyl)aniline (7g)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 95:5, 33 mg, 54%, 54% *ee*; using **C2** (10 mol%): 13 mg, 21%, 50% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 7.37-7.31 (m, 2H), 7.27-7.21 (m, 3H), 6.79-6.74 (m, 2H), 6.58-6.52 (m, 2H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 3.31 (dd, *J* = 12.2, 6.1 Hz, 1H), 3.20 (dd, *J* = 12.2, 8.3 Hz, 1H), 3.05 (sext, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 1H), 1.33 (d, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 152.10, 144.60, 142.29, 128.64, 127.24, 126.57, 114.87, 114.36, 55.81, 51.99, 39.23, 19.77.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₆H₁₉NOH⁺ [M+H⁺]: 242.1545; found: 242.1538.

The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.^[5]

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Chiralpak AD column, 97:3 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 17.5 min (minor), 18.4 (major).

(R)-4-methoxy-N-((tetrahydrofuran-2-yl)methyl)aniline (7h)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 60:40, 23 mg, 45%, 84% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 6.80-6.75 (m, 2H), 6.66-6.61 (m, 2H), 4.16-4.09 (m, 1H), 3.93-3.84 (m, 1H), 3.82-3.72 (m, 1H; s, 3H), 3.21 (dd, *J* = 12.2, 3.7 Hz, 1H), 3.04 (dd, *J* = 12.2, 7.7 Hz, 1H), 2.07-1.98 (m, 1H), 1.97-1.86 (m, 2H), 1.70-1.60 (m, 1H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 152.17, 142.58, 114.80, 114.41, 77.59, 68.03, 55.78, 49.32, 29.12, 25.82.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₂H₁₇NO₂H⁺ [M+H⁺]: 208.1338; found: 208.1331.

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Chiralpak AD column, 97:3 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 27.4 min (minor), 29.2 (major).

(S)-N-((2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)methyl)-4-methoxyaniline (7i)

Following the **General procedure**, the product was obtained as yellow oil (purification by flash column chromatography: pentane/EtOAc 60:40, 19 mg, 32%, 92% *ee*).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ 6.81-6.76 (m, 2H), 6.64-6.58 (m, 2H), 4.40-4.32 (m, 1H), 4.09 (dd, *J* = 8.1, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 3.77 (dd, *J* = 8.1, 6.7, 1H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 3.26 (dd, *J* = 12.4, 4.2 Hz, 1H), 3.15 (dd, *J* = 12.4, 6.7 Hz, 1H), 1.45 (s, 3H), 1.38 (s, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ 152.40, 142.15, 114.87, 114.43, 109.43, 74.62, 67.26, 55.78, 47.71, 26.92, 25.35.

HRMS (EI⁺) calculated for C₁₃H₁₉NO₃H⁺ [*M*+H⁺]: 238.1443; found: 238.1438.

Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Chiralpak AD column, 97:3 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min. Retention times: 25.2 min (major), 26.5 (minor).

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra

Supplementary Figure 2: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 3a.

Supplementary Figure 3: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 3b.

Supplementary Figure 4: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 3c.

Supplementary Figure 5: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **3d**.

Supplementary Figure 6: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 3e.

Supplementary Figure 7: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **3f**.

Supplementary Figure 8: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **3g**.

Supplementary Figure 9: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 3h.

Supplementary Figure 10: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **3i**.

Supplementary Figure 11: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **3j**.

Supplementary Figure 12: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **3k**.

Supplementary Figure 13: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **31** (the aliphatic region is zoomed in the small box).

Supplementary Figure 14: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **3m**.

Supplementary Figure 15: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **3n**.

Supplementary Figure 16: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 30.

Supplementary Figure 17: ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl_3) of compound **5a**.

Supplementary Figure 18: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 5b.

Supplementary Figure 19: ^1H and ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl_3) of compound **5c**.

Supplementary Figure 20: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 5d.

Supplementary Figure 21: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 5e.

Supplementary Figure 23: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of (*R*)-Cinacalcet.

Supplementary Figure 24: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **7a**.

Supplementary Figure 25: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **7b**.

Supplementary Figure 26: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 7c.

Supplementary Figure 27: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **7d**.

Supplementary Figure 28: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **7e**.

Supplementary Figure 29: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, C₆D₆) of compound **7f**.

Supplementary Figure 30: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound 7g.

Supplementary Figure 31: ¹H and ¹³C NMR (400 MHz and 101 MHz, CDCl₃) of compound **7h**.

Enantiomeric excess determination by chiral GC and HPLC

Enantiomeric excess of compounds **3a-3h** and **3l-3m** was determined by a GC-FID equipped with a Chiralsil Dex CB column. The temperature program for each compound is described above and a representative GC trace for compound **3a** is provided below (**Supplementary Figure 33**).

Supplementary Figure 33: GC trace for the racemic (top) and enantiopure *N*-acetyl derivative of (*R*)-**3a** (bottom).

Enantiomeric excess of compound **3i** was determined by chiral HPLC and the corresponding trace is shown below (**Supplementary Figure 34**).

Supplementary Figure 34: HPLC trace of racemic (top) and enantiopure (*R*)-**3i** (bottom).

Enantiomeric excess of compounds **3j**, **3k** and **5e** was determined by chiral HPLC (see conditions above) and a representative trace for compound **3j** is provided below (**Supplementary Figure 35**).

Supplementary Figure 35: HPLC trace of racemic (top) and enantiopure (*R*)-**3j** (bottom).

Enantiomeric excess of compounds **3n** and **3o** was determined by chiral HPLC (see conditions above) and a representative trace for compound **3n** is provided below (**Supplementary Figure 36**).

Supplementary Figure 36: HPLC trace of the racemic (top) and enantiopure (*S*)-**3n** (bottom).

Enantiomeric excess of compounds **5a-5d** was determined by GC-FID equipped with a Chiralsil Dex CB column. The temperature program for each compound is described above and a representative GC trace for compound **5a** is provided below (**Supplementary Figure 37**).

Supplementary Figure 37: GC trace of racemic (top) and enantiopure (**R**)-**5a** (bottom).

Enantiomeric excess of (*R*)-Fendiline was determined by chiral HPLC (see conditions above).

Supplementary Figure 38: HPLC trace of racemic (top) and (*R*)-Fendiline (bottom).

Enantiomeric excess of (*R*)-Cinacalcet was determined by chiral HPLC (see conditions above).

Supplementary Figure 39: HPLC trace of racemic (top) and (*R*)-Cinacalcet (bottom).

Enantiomeric excess of compounds **7a-7d** was determined by chiral HPLC (see conditions above for each compound) and a representative trace for compound **7a** is provided below (**Supplementary Figure 40**).

Supplementary Figure 40: HPLC traces of racemic (top) and scalemic compound **7a** (bottom, 92/8 enantiomeric ratio, **Table 1** in the main text of the manuscript, entry 1).

Enantiomeric excess of compounds **7e-7g** was determined by chiral HPLC (see conditions above for each compound) and a representative trace for compound **7e** is provided below (**Supplementary Figure 41**).

Supplementary Figure 41: HPLC traces of racemic (top) and scalemic compound **7e** (bottom).

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